

BUILT 01

Basic

Why paying attention to ageing needs and functional difficulties in terms of house design is important at younger age

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BUILT

MODULE 1

Basic

In this module you will learn why paying attention to ageing needs and functional difficulties in terms of house design is important at younger age. The duration of this module is 1 hour.

What will you learn

- 1 Why apartment adaptation should be made before you get old
- 2 What should be taken into consideration in the process of adaptation of your apartment

Module summary

1

Start apartment adaptation earlier

2

Pay attention to ageing needs and functional difficulties

3

Make an assessment and plan

4

Choose low maintenance solutions

5

Choose SMART appliances

6

Check available financial options

Start apartment adaptation earlier

Ageing-in-place often requires changing of built environment. Paying attention to ageing needs and functional difficulties should start before someone gets old. Here are several reasons for that.

First of all, some physical or physiological difficulties may occur gradually and can be observable when people are in their 50 or 60. Adapting an apartment earlier gives a person enough time for appropriate preparation and design. Moreover, if sudden deterioration of health occurs they are prepared.

Secondly, more time for adaptation gives an opportunity to think over and make reasonable choices in terms of adjustment to specific needs,

functionality, design, maintenance or possible costs of adaptation.

Decisions about adaptation are for years so they should be considered carefully, sometimes with professional help.

Moreover, in general, financial situation of people in their 50s is much better than people in their 70s, 80s or 90s. Adaptation may be costly and at the age of 50, when people still work, perspective of getting a mortgage seems feasible. When a person is 90+ financial burden can be unbearable. Furthermore, no hustle in adaptation gives also opportunity to research and compare available products and choose cheaper ones.

Pay attention to ageing needs and functional difficulties

Deterioration of health and functional abilities are signs of the last time to take an action in terms of apartment adaptation.

If you are a family member of an older person or a caregiver and you observe how the older person gets around the house.

If you notice first signs of difficulties start acting quickly. It is late but not too late to take an action.

If you do not live with an older person you may not be aware of the struggles of the older adult.

You can also talk with her or his doctor or other health care professional who may give you an insight on the abilities and areas of difficulty of the older adult. First signs of deteriorated health means that it is the last time for the assessment of older adult's housing conditions and changing them.

Make an assessment and plan

Make an assessment of the housing conditions of the older adult according to their existing and foreseen needs and difficulties. Take into consideration health problems including mental illnesses as well.

Go through the house, room-by-room, looking for problem areas like potential tripping or slipping hazards, as well as areas that are hard to access and difficult to maintain.

Suggest considering to get a professional assessment of the apartment. Specialists may help in identification of possible risks and future needs as well as making detailed project of adaptation with estimated costs.

Make a plan of adaptation based on gathered information from assessment and from the specialist.

Choose low-maintenance solutions

Products and solutions that require little or no maintenance, for example flameproof paints, solid surface countertops with a pattern, wooden furniture are easier in everyday use. These products will offer mutual benefits of good looks, long lasting performance and easy cleaning.

Pay special attention to materials. Solid ones are more expensive, however wooden doors can be used more than 100 years.

Choose SMART appliances

Smart appliances, such as stoves that notify person with a beep when they turn on or that have controls that light up are real help to older homeowners.

In the case that the senses of the older adults are weaker or people get a bit forgetful about whether or not they've turned off the oven SMART appliances help to keep them safe and independent for longer.

Home automation is another important component of ageing-in-place improvements. Sensors and timers can monitor house systems to alert homeowners, as well as care and security providers, to potential problems.

If you want to learn more you can go to SMART modules.

Check available financial options

The costs of adaptation may be high, so checking carefully available funding options is vital. There is a wide variety of programmes or grants which financially support adaptation of older adults' home.

For example in Poland bathroom refurbishment for a person with disabilities can be paid from the State Fund for the Rehabilitation of the Disabled. Governmental and local government agencies may be helpful.

If current savings of older adult do not allow for the adaptation and she or he cannot receive funding, then mortgage or a loan can be taken into consideration as well.

Module completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this module!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You have learned about the need of early adaptation of your apartment and what is important during the preparation and adaptation process.

2

This knowledge will help you to understand the importance of the quality of built environment in terms of older persons' wellbeing and health.

3

You may help other facilitators to understand the ageing-in-place process.

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 BUILT **MODULE 1** Basic

What things are important if you thinking about an older person's home adaptation?

- Checking financial opportunities
- Seniors' changing needs
- Low maintenance solutions and products
- Time for checking and comparing products
- SMART appliances
- A plan of adaptation
- A house assessment

What is next?

Now you can repeat the module, follow our study recommendation or go to the next one by clicking on one of the buttons below.

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